

Housing as a Basic Need for Human

Author Details: Shazila Andleeb

ABSTRACT RELATED TO HOUSING INDUSTRY

PURPOSE: *The purpose of this research paper is to examine analyzing and outlining the growth of the housing industry and its rights. The main purpose is to eliminate the problem related to the relevancy and application of housing complexities and its systems across the world.*

DESIGN OR METHODOLOGY: *This paper is set out according to the principle instruments and the rights of development of housing regional and other related bodies. The analysis of the housing system is basically organized on the basis of housing system of development and channels and networks of legal and lawful means of professional concerns and their domains.*

FINDINGS: *All across the world the rights for housing is being considered as a lawful and constitutional concerned nationally and internationally. The findings also suggest the significance of housing rights and the conceptual frame work of human rights effect the implementation. Professional epistemic community development of the housing shape the policies and procedures and laws. The paradiagm of housing foundation and rights are effectively translated into developed fashion of designing housing system.*

RESULTS: *Collection of data through the questionnaire are based on 7 likert scale throughout and the findings estimation is dependable more over the cost and benefit analysis. Primary data are collected through survey, questionnaire and observation and secondary data are collected through books , articles , research papers , journals , literature , published material , other sources , print media article collection , magazines , newspapers , published electronic services , e-journals , websites , weblogs , unpublished general records , government records health education and census data , public and private sector records and retrospective information. To analysis the data statistical package for social sciences software has been used. Correlation and regression analysis of cost and benefit analysis shows the mean value of 5.2822 and standard deviation of 1.54744.*

CONCLUSION: *In short the conclusion is that the wave of market economy downturn has a greater strength into its own self financially and the research study proofs that conducting the research study is crucial and beneficial towards the societal developmental factors.*

LIMITATIONS FOR RESEARCH:

The required research is not enough for the development of housing project management as a whole or specifically the example of effectiveness of the rights of housing and its elements of its whole system implication.

Keywords: *Housing, Building, Finance, Development, Environment, Taxation, Cost, Affordability, Hypothesis, Concerns about Housing*

INTRODUCTION:

BACKGROUND AND OVERVIEW OF TOPIC:

Housing building and finance trends are all towards South Asia and also towards African Sub Saharan division because of development and increasing the size of industry world over and to reduce poverty and bringing up prosperity propensity to development in the regions. There is a major link between housing and growth and poverty development in housing finances of economic housing activity facilities formation.

A number of factors play an important role in selection of housing which is basically based on personal choices of different persons in different ways for decision making and there is different behaviors and

attitude of persons towards buying behaviors of houses differently applied situations, finances and needs for development and may renovation or selecting a more better place for good standard of living throughout life .

Environmental factors and globalization are hugely effecting the world situation as air control systems are not being applied in developing countries much as compare to the developed countries. Environmental conditions and concerns for housing is in the hand of consumer behavior dependent ably buying or selling of a house. And the old homes environmental concerns is the biggest issue in the world of house finance industry. History and theories of developmental sciences explores the development concepts of community on large scale for hose building and finance the related issue for all concerns through banking sector payments and schedules or savings etc.

In general economy industrial housing is a huge business of development and is highly cyclical changes over the world in costing the market value of the houses and the neighbourhod is is the intentional issue for all people concerned. That can bring a change to life style of the society, families, households etc by regulating the programs of agencies and other builders and developers of construction business and it involves the complete process of continuous process of changing the society as a whole .

There are privacy issues related with housing evolves placement of every item within the house in relation with the set patterned of noise pollution , activity patterns and privacy disturbances issues that includes kitchen , heating ,cooling , technology , living rooms , room arrangement , floor plan , bathrooms ,family room etc . The expensive approach is the floor plan and related changes in remodeling it . So it is difficult to be settled into the developed house as compare to undeveloped one or an old one .

Housing choices for a families or an individual is dependable on the affordability factor which is more difficult significantly for lower income groups for spending on their expenditure towards housing because it is the basic need of life such as food, shelter, clothing and temporary housing or state level property. These type of people struggles throughout life to fulfill his or her basic needs and they sometimes become homeless even if they are employed. At communist level people are trying to give the housing facilities to poor people through charities, foundations and Land trusts which only provide one unit to fulfill the requirement and are only for humanity services welfare plan of managing the control over poverty.

Humanity based workers who are providing the basic needs for human being for developing there selves in a more better way are constructing a low income group housing planned structures into the societies of there need . One should meet the monthly income requirement for paying off the debts and regular expenditure which are the basic need of all human being to spend on maintenance of their own shelter and it's the running expense.

Ownership requires alot of financial efforts which is not easy for every citizen in any country of this world. It is dependable on the purchasing power of an individual for becoming the home owner or starting the processing of buying home which is dependable on different market behaviors and power of purchasing of different human status .

Future of housing industry in Pakistan specifically in Karachi is the biggest challenge for providing safe and sound and affordable houses because of law and order situations and other political factors for the usage of land and concerns for huge or small spaces of houses for adults , olds and children and other resources allocation such as natural resources . The challenges for house, building and finance industry in 21st century includes :

Affordability of houses

Challenges for the industry

Placing according to aging groups

Community development and losses related to it

Allocation of resources in the manner able way

CONSIDERABLE FACTORS FOR HOUSING RESEARCH:

- 1 Housing affordability
- 2 Pakistan development review
- 3 Development economics
- 4 Trade and industry
- 5 Technology
- 6 Demographics , poverty and labor
- 7 Investments foreign and domestic
- 8 Financials and banking system
- 9 Market value trends and development
- 10 Improvement standing or maintenance , home repair, remodeling and green improvement
- 11 Communities development
- 12 Policy and housing finance
- 13 Home ownership
- 14 Rental plans for housing
- 15 Urbanization and housing
- 16 Housing health and social service
- 17 New innovation and ideas
- 18 Marital status and area per square feet statistical analysis
- 19 Neighborhood quality and problems
- 20 Historical changes
- 21 Industry out look
- 22 Crises
- 23 Population and development
- 24 Trends and segmentation , income , business residential etc
- 25 Foreign remittances
- 26 Population and poverty
- 27 Housing deficiencies

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY:

Housing is the basic needs of human kind world over

Houses are financial investments

Housing is the significant component of the local, regional and national economy

Housing is the social priority as declared by the US congress in 1949

International Aid Agencies

Housing Social Enterprises

Developers' Associations and Different ethnic Groups

PROBLEM STATEMENT:

There is an impact of banking market based on transactions of interest rate related to housing, building and finance?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES/PURPOSE:

Ideas to develop the country as a whole
Cost and benefits and finance analysis
To discuss the affordability
Development process for all income levels
To examine the challenges of housing developers in the low income market and hindrances to their efforts
To identify the motivation behind existent players in the industry whether profit, social or other.

RESEARCH QUESTION:

- How do you implement the developed financial structures of foreign financial institutions in Karachi Pakistan?

LITERATURE REVIEW:

The housing market theory suggests the broader way of approaches related with the house, building and finance corporations which includes the mechanism of market dynamics study and designs the structural model for housing development. It talks about localization consideration, durability, taxation of housing, maintenance etc while keeping in mind the urban structures that reach the maturity level in mid 80's. Housing is concerned for its prices measurement for the goods and services an individual wants to purchase and also concerned with the externalities related with neighborhood issues that affect the efficient market scenario in between different places and ethnic groups world over . (Franz Hubert –Humboldt University Berlin).

Housing theories are dependable over the cost , structures , imperfect information , theory and application of market forces , estate agents role etc and its features are designed for the welfare development of properties for the market of housing specially for low income groups .The imperfection of the housing market dependable over the market forces such as financial market position of international and national scenarios and their interactions which creates fluctuation in creation of market isolation.(1987 Arnott and Smith and 1988 Fallis and Rosen).

Housing factors basically depends upon market factors for example tenure choices for commodity while renting or ownership on the particular scale of measurement and analysis based theory. Housing issues are analyzed narrowly and all are focused over the demand side for consumers and suppliers, for housing exchanges on contractual basis of development and arrangements of related decision making process of businesses practice.

It differs from country to country situation of business practices that how to conduct different situations in different ways which effect renting and ownership dealing and regulation of authority. In its dealing with housing, finance and building is a complex process which focused on the principle of diversification of institutions related to durability effect of tenure choices perfection or imperfection. Complexity of the models for development involves the complicated procedures of taxation and its schemes, inflation, foreign rates, tenure time period for example renting for the cost of ownership and high income groups as compare to low income group's ownerships of homes.

CONTRACTS AND INCENTIVES THAT ARE INCOMPLETE:

The basic contracting problem of housing investment consist of few observations of mobility cost and management and for the considerable time period people want to stay in their own homes reason being valuation and psychological attachment and neighborhood issues and expensiveness and inconvenienceness of placement .

The dependable factor for housing changes are related with the changes in income of an individual and the composition of family etc and the quantitative and qualitative housing involves the movement of ex-post indivisibilities. While the change in the individual income can dynamically change the buying patterns within and outside the country desirably that turns the real cost into the moving gain that are equivalent to the negative cost of mobility which is concerned as exogenous views in the housing market analysis . But it also involves the elements of endogenous.

The investment of the occupants consists of exogenous factors as a determinant of mobility costing and analysis which is difficult to incorporate. The market value is dependably needs a continuous maintenance for accommodation and its care and utilization of it is required. In an apartment it is extended up to the common structures . These observation requires idealistic occupant that should possess a following ability

1 complete the tenure given

2 do decide upon investment

3 changes in the market

For the above given purposes rental contracting is the best to considered first and then turn it in the private ownership.

CONTRACTS THAT ARE RENTAL:

Landlords are concerned with rental arrangements and payments claim for the property value and decide upon other related field investment and the basic issue is tenure security. There can be two type of major contracts short time contract based on notices and long term contracts that are based on fixed sort of terms and conditions with the indefinite duration .

OWNERSHIP CONCERNS:

In this there is the right of occupant security rights and duties in terms of security control and for developing residential claim on property valuation in which ownership principles are of foremost important in the sense of investment, care and maintenance with the crucial practical based limitations. Decision with respect to structures are uncontrollable of house or an apartment because of income rights of occupant related to cost variation of housing department. Landlord and tenant relationship consist of many problems resulted into single occupant and the union of other related occupant for instance multiple-family or single-family houses are dependable upon availability of land energy prices and climatic condition variation over the world. Which is the basic element for determination of needs?

HETEROGENIOUS TRADING AND SEARCHING

OF THIN MARKETS:

Housing is basically a need that requires time consumption, efforts for information based on opportunity analysis for trading. The issues are same as in rental contract and ownership markets meet each other at end point which is the determinant of the exchange condition . The efficiency of the market matches the dynamic market and more interest are attached to dynamic implications. (Arnott and Igarashi 2000) develops the rental market based analysis for entering into the market of housing, tenants based information collection about the availability units.

Basically landlords differentiate the products taste and transparency resulted into market power and rental charges are above the marginal cost. And in long term bases profit triggers enters the market which strikes the equilibrium up to the 'excess' capacity. Which will form a vacant housing that is not profitable usually in the forms of modeling monopolistic competition that is not clear even in 'excessive' form?

DYNAMIC PRICES, TURNOVER RELATED VACANCIES:

Housing is the topic gaining attention as an asset in an economy and surprisingly prices based studies are related to greater history that focused features of property such as aging of product, price, place and promotion. Prices turnover failed to be incorporated in predictable movements of real estate business and it also systematically deviate from capitalization process. Once the housing wealth tied up, the initial declining process of aging starts up and some moves are related to down payment of newly built house.(Stein 1995).

One of the theory predicts the relationship of positive correlation of list prices, timing for sale and loan to valuation ratio. (Genesove and Mayer 1997).Theory of dynamic markets of housing consist of borrowing

constraints with adjustment cost etc . Increase in rental payments decreases the rate of the turnover. But in ownership markets increment in prices will relax financials concerns by which sales volume increases in both directions opposite and dynamic.

In short housing and its related finance is based on increasing attention gaining subject of matter of economics in recent years of the world of development which extant the literature of review and the observations in this particular area is a few because of human element essentially polarized (By Naik 1981) vol. 2 and according to J.P. Sah 2011 volume 3 “ housing is a growing problem but it is not static “ (Year book 1997) and as the modern concepts are developing over time of housing and shelters for the improvement of humanity and settlement of humanly factors for economic policies because this is the basic need for the society of mankind related with socio-economic factors . It is the material element of cultural aspects which do consist of threats over the physical living elements of survival that serves the meaning full purpose.

Development of housing in our country is a biggest problem and do have a magnitude effect of it over the others who do not have such concerns of home sweet home . It is a topic which consists of shortage in our country especially with regard to land ownership concerns and in the developing country like Pakistan specifically Karachi do have many barriers and hurdles of high energy efficiency in housing market.

The housing policy of public and private services consist of the methods of ownership of home cash, credit and contractual tactics etc related with the evolution of housing over the world (1945) . The market enables the opinion of the individual while involving the banking sector financing for housing that includes formal and informal budgets allocation of the state and the central governments or financial institution and commercial development of public , private sectors funding . Housing and finance is the up growing industry in South East Asia from the previous two decades and the relationship of housing loans with respect to GDP as a percentage is very lower. That emphasizes the housing importance in terms of its affordability dependable on the Pakistan finance housing system which has strong forward and backward linkages of industry conceptual frame work.

Housing is the centre for mankind which is progression material of civilization as an instrument and individual’s life is affected by the foundation of his or her moral and family life through standard of living. The foremost step in construction business is the collection of money to own it as a house and these are the days of advancement linked up with the financial institution are available over the world for helping throughout the procedure of payment plan of constructor and consumers which full fills one’s dream come true . This is a topic of great concern in our country because there is a shortage , cost effectiveness , problems of environment , significant thoughts of urban and rural developmental factors related to future housing division perspective awareness’s and effects of decentralization.

METHODOLOGY:

POPULATION:

This is the a set of elements which have some of the common built up characteristics meaningful as a relationship with sampling criteria of establishing a research based analysis . It is composed of two main groups targeting of population & accessibility of population. In which the target market population is the universe based on the researchers findings about studies dependable over a criteria designed material for instance Karachi (Pakistan) is the target population which comprises of general public and professionals and officials .

SAMPLE:

It is the selected element which is selected for contributing in a study of a subject matter of theory model.

SAMPLING:

The process for the selection of a group study based on event occurrence , behaviours of people and the elements from which the study is conducted .

SAMPLE SIZE:

It is possibly increasing the size of sample upto more than 101 respondents

SAMPLING NATURE:

It is the process of selection of a number of studies units which define the study of population dependable on research problem findings and research based on goals to be achieved and I used random sampling method for selection.

SELECTION:

Selection criteria involves the collection of primary secondary data subjected to the real world situations and will be selected through random sampling method.

PRIMARY DATA COLLECTION:

Primary research can be done in many ways and means related to the subject concerned that is basically dependable on research.

INTERVIEWS:

It can be conducted face to face in small group sessions for questions and answers that will provide alot of collected information from limited people but with knowledgeable information about the subject opinion and concerns.

SURVEYS:

These are the questioning form of interview based involvement from a large group of people from which we gather information from number of people for population target and specific and individual assessable thinking.

OBSERVATION:

Involves continuous improvement of occurrence of the whole world and it provides specification like event , people etc .

ANALYSIS:

Analysis involves the data collection that is developed by the researcher and it can be easily recognize through records.

QUESTIONNAIRE:

There will be both closed ended questions as well as open ended questions so it is concerned about the mixed approach for gathering information.

SECONDARY DATA COLLECTION:

Books , articles , research papers , journals , literature , published material , other sources , print media article collection , magazines , newspapers , published electronic services , e-journals , websites , weblogs , unpublished general records , government records health education and census data , public and private sector records and retrospective information .

VARIABLES DEPENDENT AND INDEPENDENT:

DEPENDENT VARIABLE:

House, building and finance interest rate effects of sectors and institution

INDEPENDABLE VARIABLES:

Housing as a shelter is one of the basic needs for man kind

Cost and benefits and finance analysis

International and national Aid Agencies

To discuss the affordability

Ideas to develop the country as a whole

To observe the challenges faced by housing developers in the low income market and hindrances to their efforts

Housing is not important to be linked up with Priority groups for housing financing policy matters

Real estate and financial market factors for development

Housing market trend and development

Rental housing, programs and policy

Urbanization and housing

Real estate and financial market factors for development

HYPOTHESIS NO. 1: BASIC NEED

H0: Housing is not the one of the basic need for man kind

H1: housing is the one of the basic need for man kind

HYPOTHESIS NO. 2: COST AND BENEFIT ANALYSIS

H0: cost benefits and financial analysis is important or not

H2: cost benefits and financial analysis is important

HYPOTHESIS NO. 3: AGENCIES

H0: Housing agencies does not play an important role

H3: Housing agencies does play an important role

HYPOTHESIS NO. 4:AFFORDABILITY

H0: Affordability is not dependable over the income of an individual

H4: Affordability is dependable over the income of an individual

HYPOTHESIS NO. 5:IDEAS FOR DEVELOPMENT

H0: Ideas not towards the development of the country

H5: Ideas towards the development of the country

HYPOTHESIS NO. 6: CHALLENGES FACED

H0: To observe the challenges faced by housing developers is not important in the low income market and is not hindrance to their efforts

H6: To observe the challenges faced by housing developers in the low income market and hindrances to their efforts

HYPOTHESIS NO. 7: FINANCING POLICY

H0: Housing is not important to be linked up with Priority groups for housing financing policy matters

H7: Housing is important to be linked up with Priority groups for housing financing policy matters

HYPOTHESIS NO. 8: FINANCIAL FACTORS OF MARKET

H0: Real estate and financial market factors are not significant for development

H8: Real estate and financial market factors is significant for development

HYPOTHESIS NO. 9: MARKET TREND

Ho: Housing market trend and development is not linked up

H9: Housing market trend and development is linked up

HYPOTHESIS NO. 10: ENTITLEMENTSHIP

H0: Rental housing , programs , policy and Urbanization housing is not important

H10: Rental housing , programs , policy and Urbanization housing is important

DATA ANALYSIS: DESCRIPTIVE:

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
housingasabasicneed	101	2.25	7.00	5.1683	.90768
costandbenefitanalysis	101	3.50	6.75	5.1337	.76286
nationalinternationalagencie s	101	1.00	6.75	4.9381	.90789
affordability	101	2.50	7.00	5.1015	.79779
ideasfordevelopment	101	2.00	6.50	5.0173	.87125
challengesfaced	101	3.50	7.00	5.1634	.73692
financialpolicies	101	2.50	6.25	4.8441	.77850
nationalandinternationalage ncies	101	1.00	6.75	4.9381	.90789
financialfactorsofthemarket	101	2.75	6.50	5.0198	.76296
marketrends	101	2.75	6.75	4.9901	.76805
entitlementship	101	3.00	6.75	5.0272	.72189
Valid N (listwise)	101				

INTERPRETATION:

According to respondent’s opinions the rating on dependent variable housing as a basic need consist of the mean value of 5.1683 which one is first highest and the second highest mean value is of the challenges faced with the mean of 5.1634 and the third highest value is of the variable related to cost and benefit analysis with the mean of 5.1337 and the other variables mean is lower as compare to these three.

The standard deviation according to the respondent opinion was highest in cost analysis that is 1.54744, which one is highest as compare to other variables used.

CORRELATIONS:

		housing as a basic need	cost and benefit analysis	national international agencies	affordability	ideas for development	challenges faced	challenges faced	financial policies	national and international agencies	financial factors of the market	market trends
Housing as a basic need	Pearson Correlation	1	0.302053609	-0.018329955	0.04506882	0.202549787	0.066869097	0.066869097	0.180132	-0.018329955	0.087193795	0.125236729
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.00214611	0.855632894	0.00135955	0.042217486	0.506430858	0.506430858	0.070395698	0.855632894	0.385924307	0.212079862
	N	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101
Cost and benefit analysis	Pearson Correlation	0.302053609	1	0.123058294	0.03954346	0.162924195	0.33213672	0.33213672	0.031238202	0.123058294	0.065205835	0.076950843
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00214611		0.220201469	0.024361725	0.103549553	0.00661821	0.00661821	0.756478798	0.220201469	0.517086066	0.44435765
	N	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101
affordability	Pearson Correlation	0.314506882	0.223954346	0.095909656	1	0.135919263	0.16925326	0.16925326	0.121334786	0.095909656	0.230777949	0.05469628

												4
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.0 013 595 5	0.024 3617 25	0.340 04105 5		0.17 533 232 6	0.0 90 63 97 98	0.0 90 63 97 98	0.2 26 78 08 95	0.3400 41055	0.020 2406 88	0. 58 69 53 81 1
	N	101	101	101	10 1	101	10 1	10 1	10 1	101	101	10 1
Ideas for development	Pearson Correlation	0.2 025 497 87	0.162 9241 95	0.292 14266 7	0. 13 59 19 26 3	1	0.2 52 54 21 83	0.2 52 54 21 83	- 0.0 16 24 88 18	0.2921 42667	0.238 2994 16	0. 14 12 93 63 2
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.0 422 174 86	0.103 5495 53	0.003 03265 5	0. 17 53 32 32 6		0.0 10 83 83 63	0.0 10 83 83 63	0.8 71 87 55 48	0.0030 32655	0.016 4063 1	0. 15 87 19 90 9
	N	101	101	101	10 1	101	10 1	10 1	10 1	101	101	10 1
Challenges faced	Pearson Correlation	0.0 668 690 97	0.333 2136 72	0.069 44384 2	0. 16 92 53 26	0.25 254 218 3	1	1	- 0.1 26 19 15 52	0.0694 43842	0.375 4793 1	0. 15 19 61 96 6
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.5 064 308 58	0.000 6618 21	0.490 16356	0. 09 06 39 79 8	0.01 083 836 3	0		0.2 08 58 81 29	0.4901 6356	0.000 1092 31	0. 12 92 63 09
	N	101	101	101	10 1	101	10 1	10 1	10 1	101	101	10 1
Financial policies	Pearson Correlation	0.1 808 013 2	0.031 2382 02	- 0.197 71948 6	0. 12 13 34 78 6	- 0.01 624 881 8	- 0.1 26 19 15 52	- 0.1 26 19 15 52	1	- 0.1977 19486	- 0.087 3474 57	0. 16 15 00 35 5
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.0 703 956 98	0.756 4787 98	0.047 48656 1	0. 22 67 80 89 5	0.87 187 554 8	0.2 08 58 81 29	0.2 08 58 81 29		0.0474 86561	0.385 0844 79	0. 10 66 43 20 1
	N	101	101	101	10 1	101	10 1	10 1	10 1	101	101	10 1

National and international agencies	Pearson Correlation	-0.018329955	0.123058294	1	0.095909656	0.292142667	0.069443842	0.069443842	-0.19719486	1	0.116378122	0.026898223
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.855632894	0.220201469	0	0.340041055	0.003032655	0.490163566	0.490163566	0.047486561		0.246468207	0.789463
	N	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101
Financial factors of the market	Pearson Correlation	0.087193795	0.065205835	0.116378122	0.023077949	0.238294166	0.375479311	0.375479311	-0.0878347457	0.116378122	1	0.143258572
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.385924307	0.517086066	0.246468207	0.0240688	0.0164002631	0.00109231	0.00109231	0.385084479	0.246468207		0.15294867
	N	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101
Market trends	Pearson Correlation	0.125236729	0.076950843	0.026898223	0.04696284	0.14129362	0.196666	0.196666	0.1610355	0.026898223	0.143258572	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.212079862	0.44435765	0.789463538	0.586953811	0.158719909	0.129263099	0.129263099	0.106643201	0.789463538	0.15294867	
	N	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101
Entitlement ship	Pearson Correlation	0.18465751	0.109086768	0.075071915	0.05613761	0.18308195	0.287916363	0.287916363	-0.027279696	0.075071915	0.067097555	0.101943284
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.064513123	0.277520225	0.45559121	0.249606	0.06686499	0.0213224	0.0213224	0.7813798	0.45559121	0.50497624	0.310386

					02 9		14	14	26			89 9
	N	101	101	101	10 1	101	10 1	10 1	10 1	101	101	10 1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

INTERPRETATION:

According to statistical package for social sciences(SPSS) software the correlation and regression analysis indicates the relationship between the two individual variable and there is positive relationship between housing as a basic need, cost and benefit analysis, national international agencies involvement, affordability, ideas for development, challenges faced, financial policies, financial factors of the market, market trend and entitlementship.

The dependent variable “housing as a basic need” has the strongest correlation of (0.314) with affordability, with ideas for development (0.202) and so on as shown in the table above.

Variables Entered/Removed^b

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	entitlementship, costandbenefitan alysis, financialpolicies, financialfactorso fthemarket, nationalinternati onalagencies, affordability, markettrend, ideasfordevelop ment, challengesfaced ^a		Enter

a. All requested variables entered.

b. Dependent Variable: housingasabasicneed

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.477 ^a	.228	.152	.83606

a. Predictors: (Constant), entitlementship, financialpolicies, financialfactorsofthemarket, costandbenefitanalysis, marketrends, nationalandinternationalagencies, affordability, ideasfordevelopment, challengesfaced

INTERPRETATION:

The R value show Coefficient of Correlation is the numerical measure of strength of the linear relationship between two variables. The R value (.477^a) is show that there is positive correlation between Two variables.

The R Square show Coefficient of Determination defines the square of Coefficient of Correlation. The R Square values (.228) mean 23% reliable to be used for estimation of population.

The Std. Error is important because they reflect how much sampling Fluctuation a statistic will show. The Std.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.790	1.219		.648	.519
	costandbenefitanalysis	.305	.120	.256	2.541	.013
	affordability	.259	.112	.228	2.311	.023
	ideasfordevelopment	.159	.106	.153	1.499	.137
	challengesfaced	-.156	.135	-.127	-1.154	.252
	financialpolicies	.127	.115	.109	1.108	.271
	nationalandinternational agencies	-.101	.099	-.101	-1.021	.310
	financialfactorsofthemarket	.039	.124	.033	.319	.750
	marketrends	.068	.113	.057	.599	.551
	entitlementship	.168	.121	.134	1.395	.167

a. Dependent Variable: housingasabasicneed

INTERPRETATION:

The Std. Error is important because they reflect how much sampling fluctuation a statistic will show. The St.d Error of a statistic depends on the sample size in the general the larger sample of the St.d Error. St.d Error of Constant (1.219). Standardized Coefficients are the coefficient that you would obtain if the Predictors and the outcomes variable were standardized prior the analysis and the Comparing the size of the coefficient across variable.

The t value of Independent Variable financial cost of the market is (0.750). According to the rules if t value is greater that 2 (t>2.5) than null hypothesis will be rejected and alternate hypothesis will be accepted.

CONCLUSION:

The housing demand has been rapidly growing specially expansion in urbanization is increasing through migrant cases concerned with rural area migration toward development and increasing their standard of living through migration. So that they can realize the differentiation in standard of living as compare to rural areas. The unhygienic condition is the basic problem in rural areas where there is a undeveloped and uneven structures of mud and clays and red bricks constructions which causes different problems and disease to the society. Usually the drawback of housing industry is lack of funding on large scale project of housing. The latest researches shows that the privatized sector is capable to secure the cheap finances and the change in the last decade shows that the industry of housing is related to market forces functioning as a whole and on large scale for developers concerned people.

In short the conclusion is that the wave of market economy downturn has a greater strength into its own self financially and the research study proofs that conducting the research study is crucial and beneficial towards the societal developmental factors. And the construction businesses have its great future in upcoming days for an industrial development of trade commerce and industry of ministry of finance and development segmentation and positioning successfully in future.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Research related to housing make us understand the possibilities of development to build, afford and to bridge the finance or capital in a particular direction for gaining benefits based on different governmental and private procedures and policies regarding to housing. The government provides the suitable infrastructure and lands that are required for housing and development projects such as the high demand market of housing industry framework by the large developers and builders within and outside the country.

It involves the strategic process based on internal and external factors focused on the construction of developed and undeveloped structures and the strategy is the large segment for positioning of the buyers to develop their own homes, houses, flats, bungalows, palaces etc. However the housing affordability is the basic and main issue for the entire world.

REFERENCES:

- i. *Wps.prenhall.com. n.p. Housing Challenges for the 21st Century.[online] Available at: http://wps.prenhall.com/chet_hera_introhousing_1/58/14849/3801348.cw/index.html [Accessed: 4 Jul 2013]*
- ii. *Drakakis, D. 2013. literature.Cockbum.C. (1 971) 'Construction in overseas development, Ekislies Vol. 31, No.186, p.347- 52, 31 (186), pp. 347-352. Available at: http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/73/20/9_chapter2.pdf [Accessed: 4th July , 2013].*
- iii. *Smith, Lawrence B.; Rosen, Kenneth, T.; Fallis, George (1988) Recent Developments*
- iv. *in Economic Models for Housing Markets, Journal of Economic Literature Review,*
- v. *vol. XXVI(march), pp. 29–64*
- vi. *Veronica Cacad Warnock and Francis E. Warnock Journal of Housing Economics, 2008, vol. 17, issue 3, pages 239-251*
- vii. *Abt. Associates inc. 2013 targeting housing production subsidies abt. Associates inc. ,3 (5) , pp. 1-30 . available at : <http://www.huduser.org/publication/pdf/targetinglitreview.pdf> (Accessed : 13th august ,2013)*
- viii. *“An assessment of the Indian housing finance system:crucial perspective.” journal of business and management 5 ,5 (2013): 12-24 <http://iosrjournal.org/isor-jbm/vol5-issue5/B0551124.pdf>*
- ix. *Shodhganga “review of literature” 2013 web(Accesses: 13 August ,2013) http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/bitstream/10603/73/20/9_chapter2.p (By Naik 1981) vol. 2 and according to J.P. Sah 2011 volume 3 “ housing is a growing problem but it is not static “ (Year book 1997)*
- x. *Arnott, R. and M. Igarashi (2000) Rent control, mismatch costs and search efficiency, Regional*

- xi. *Science and Urban Economics*, 30, 249-288.
- xii. ENGLUND, PETER. “The choice of methodology for computing housing price indexes: comparison of temporal aggregation and sample definition “ *journal of real estate finance and economics*”, 19, 2 (2013): 1-5 http://urbanpolicy.berkeley.edu/pdf/EQR_JREFE99.pdf Ideas.repec.org. 1879. David Genesove at IDEAS, [online] Available at <http://ideas.repec.org/e/pge30.html> [Accessed Date : 14th august, 2013].
- xiii. Hubert, F. (1999), *Optimale Finanzkontrakte, Investitionspolitik und Wettbewerbskraft, Studies in Contemporary Economics, Physica/Springer, Heidelberg*
- xiv. Hubert, F. (1998), *Private Rented Housing in Germany, Netherlands Journal of Housing and the Built Environment Vol. 13(3), S. 205-232*